

A Comparative Analysis of Constitutional Alteration Procedures in Nigeria and Ghana

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Abstract:

This paper undertakes a comparative analysis of the constitution alteration procedures in Nigeria and Ghana, with a view to examining how each system balances the competing demands of constitutional rigidity and adaptability. It interrogates the legal frameworks governing constitution alteration in both jurisdictions, focusing on section 9 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 and articles 289-290 of the 1992 Constitution of Ghana. The paper reveals that while both countries adopt rigid constitutional models, Nigeria relies on a federal, legislature-driven process requiring multi-level approval, whereas Ghana incorporates direct popular participation through referendums, particularly for entrenched provisions. The paper argues that these differing approaches have produced distinct practical outcomes. Nigeria's model, though complex and elite-driven, has facilitated incremental constitutional reform, while Ghana's stringent referendum thresholds, requiring both high voter turnout and supermajority approval, have often impeded successful amendments. The analysis further highlights key challenges, including limited public participation in Nigeria, excessive rigidity in Ghana, and concerns regarding institutional roles such as the involvement of the Council of State. The paper concludes by proposing reforms aimed at enhancing both efficiency and legitimacy, including clarifying procedural ambiguities, strengthening civic engagement, and recalibrating amendment thresholds. It contends that a balanced approach is essential to ensuring that constitutions remain both stable and responsive to changing governance needs.

Keywords: Constitution Alteration, Amendment, Nigeria, Ghana, Referenda, Federalism, Constitutional Rigidity.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Constitutions are designed to endure as the supreme legal framework of a state, yet they must also remain sufficiently adaptable to respond to changing political, social, and economic realities. The process of constitutional alteration is therefore carefully structured to strike a delicate balance between stability and flexibility. While rigidity serves as a safeguard against impulsive or politically expedient changes, excessive inflexibility may hinder necessary reforms and weaken the responsiveness of governance systems.¹ Consequently, constitutional amendment procedures are not merely technical devices; they are central to the legitimacy, durability, and democratic character of constitutional orders.²

In comparative constitutional scholarship, amendment procedures are often viewed as indicators of how a polity negotiates the tension between continuity and change.³ Systems that concentrate amendment powers within political institutions may prioritise stability and elite consensus, whereas those that incorporate direct democratic mechanisms tend to emphasise popular sovereignty and participatory legitimacy. It is within this broader theoretical context that the constitutional experiences of Nigeria and Ghana become particularly instructive.

Nigeria and Ghana, two leading constitutional democracies in West Africa, adopt distinct approaches to constitutional alteration shaped by their institutional structures and historical trajectories. Nigeria operates a federal system under the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999, which prescribes a highly rigid, legislature-driven alteration process requiring supermajority approval at both the national and subnational levels.⁴ Ghana, by contrast, operates a unitary constitutional system under the 1992 Constitution, which adopts a differentiated approach by distinguishing between entrenched and non-entrenched provisions, with the former subject to approval through a national referendum.⁵ This divergence reflects broader constitutional philosophies.

While Nigeria emphasises federal balance and institutional control, Ghana incorporates elements of participatory constitutionalism through direct citizen involvement. The comparison is particularly significant in the context of democratic consolidation in Africa, where questions of legitimacy, inclusion, and constitutional stability remain central.⁶ This article therefore undertakes a comparative analysis of the constitutional alteration procedures in both countries, with a view to identifying their implications for democratic governance and suggesting pathways for reform.

¹ J N Aduba and S Oguce, *Key Issues in Nigerian Constitutional Law* (Lambert Academic Publishing, 2014) 49

² R Albert, 'Constitutional Amendments and Constitutional Dismemberment' [2018] 43 *Yale Journal of International Law* 1, 4.

³ Y Roznai, *Unconstitutional Constitutional Amendments: The Limits of Amendment Powers* (Oxford University Press 2017) 12.

⁴ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999, s 9.

⁵ Constitution of the Republic of Ghana 1992, arts 289-292.

⁶ V C Jackson, 'Constitutional Amendment and Transnational Constitutionalism' (2010) 64 *American Journal of Comparative Law* 1, 6.

2. CONCEPTUALIZING CONSTITUTIONAL ALTERATION AND DEMOCRATIC GOVERNANCE

Constitution alteration is a fundamental feature of constitutionalism, reflecting the need for legal systems to balance continuity with change. It refers to the formal process through which provisions of a constitution are modified in accordance with prescribed procedures. In democratic systems, this process is deeply connected to questions of legitimacy, participation, and the distribution of political power.⁷ Existing studies emphasise that alteration rules are designed to safeguard the constitution against arbitrary changes while allowing for adaptation to evolving societal needs.⁸ Constitution alteration engages the tension between constitutional rigidity and democratic responsiveness. Rigid amendment procedures, typically involving supermajorities, multiple institutional approvals, or referenda, serve as safeguards against transient political majorities seeking to entrench power.⁹ However, excessive rigidity may impede necessary reforms and weaken the capacity of the state to respond to emerging challenges.¹⁰ As Albert argues, alteration procedures are central to preserving the identity of a constitution, and attempts to fundamentally alter its core structure may amount to “constitutional dismemberment” rather than mere alteration.¹¹

Democratic governance further requires that constitutional alteration processes reflect principles of popular sovereignty and inclusiveness. Increasingly, scholars advocate participatory mechanisms, such as referenda and public consultations, as means of enhancing legitimacy and public trust.¹² This is particularly relevant in transitional and consolidating democracies, where constitutional change often carries significant political and social implications. In the African context, constitution alteration processes are shaped by historical experiences, institutional arrangements, and the imperative of democratic consolidation. According to Roznai, the design of amendment procedures determines both how constitutions change, and how they endure.¹³ Accordingly, understanding constitution alteration requires an appreciation of both its legal structure and its broader role in sustaining democratic governance.

3. CONSTITUTIONAL ALTERATION IN NIGERIA

The procedure for constitution alteration in Nigeria is principally governed by section 9 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999. This provision establishes a rigid and multi-layered amendment process, reflecting the framers’ intention to safeguard the supremacy and stability of the Constitution while accommodating the

⁷ T Ginsburg and J Melton, ‘Does the Constitutional Amendment Rule Matter at All? Amendment Cultures and the Challenges of Measuring Amendment Difficulty’ [2015] 13 *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 686, 687.

⁸ R Albert, *Constitutional Amendments: Making, Breaking, and Changing Constitutions* (Oxford University Press 2019) 3.

⁹ K C Wheare, *Modern Constitutions* (Oxford University Press 1966) 67.

¹⁰ Rosalind Dixon and David Landau, ‘Tiered Constitutional Design’ (2015) 86 *George Washington Law Review* 438, 441.

¹¹ R Albert, ‘Constitutional Amendments and Constitutional Dismemberment’ [2018] 43 *Yale Journal of International Law* 1, 3.

¹² S Levinson, *Our Undemocratic Constitution* (Oxford University Press 2006) 167

¹³ Y Roznai, *Unconstitutional Constitutional Amendments: The Limits of Amendment Powers* (Oxford University Press 2017) 12.

federal character of the Nigerian state. The Constitution distinguishes between different categories of constitutional provisions and prescribes varying thresholds for their amendment. Under section 9(2), a bill for the alteration of the Constitution must be passed by not less than two-thirds majority of all the members of each House of the National Assembly, that is, the Senate and the House of Representatives.¹⁴ In addition, such a bill must be approved by the resolution of not less than two-thirds of all the State Houses of Assembly.¹⁵ This dual requirement ensures that constitution alterations reflect both national legislative consensus and subnational endorsement, thereby reinforcing Nigeria's federal structure. For more sensitive provisions, the Constitution¹⁶ imposes a higher threshold, requiring the approval of not less than four-fifths majority of all the members of each House of the National Assembly, in addition to the approval of two-thirds of State Houses of Assembly. These provisions typically relate to fundamental aspects of the constitutional order, such as the creation of states, creation of new local government areas and other core structural elements.

It is important to state that the Constitution expressly affirms the power of the National Assembly to alter the Constitution, subject to the procedures prescribed in the section¹⁷, while section 9(4) (as introduced by subsequent amendments) provides for the timelines within which State Houses of Assembly are to consider alteration bills.⁵ The cumulative effect of section 9 is to entrench a highly rigid alteration framework, combining supermajority requirements with federal participation. It has been rightly observed that such rigidity is designed to prevent arbitrary or frequent constitutional changes while ensuring that any alteration commands broad political consensus.¹⁸ However, it has also been criticised for making constitutional reform cumbersome and limiting adaptability.¹⁹ It is obvious that the procedure reflects Nigeria's federal structure and embodies a carefully calibrated distribution of powers among key institutions.

3.1 The role of the National Assembly

Constitutional alteration in Nigeria occupies a central place in the constitutional architecture of the state. The process is deliberately rigorous, designed to balance flexibility with stability, thereby ensuring that the fundamental law of the land is not subject to transient political interests. At the core of this process lies the National Assembly, a bicameral legislature composed of the Senate and the House of Representatives. The functions, powers, and limitations of the National Assembly in this regard are primarily derived from Section 9 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended). The role of the National Assembly in constitutional alteration is therefore both foundational and circumscribed, reflecting Nigeria's commitment to federalism, popular sovereignty, and the rule of law.

The constitution alteration procedure in Nigeria begins within the precincts of the National Assembly. The proposal for alteration of the Constitution must be advanced

¹⁴ Section 9

¹⁵ Ibid

¹⁶ section 9(3)

¹⁷ section 9(1)

¹⁸ S Oguche, 'Constitutional Quagmire in Kogi State: Examining the Failure of the Legislature and the Judiciary', [2017] 8 (2), *Nigerian Journal of Legislative Affairs*, 75-77

¹⁹ H I Adebawale, 'The Sixth National Assembly and Constitutional Amendment in Nigeria: A New Era or a Fait Accompli?' [2019] 2(10) *Scholars International Journal of Law, Crime and Justice* 318, 320.

deliberately and with broad support. Section 9(1) of the Constitution enjoins that any proposal for alteration must be supported by at least two-thirds of all members of both Houses of the National Assembly. This super-majority requirement serves as a critical safeguard, ensuring that constitutional alteration reflects substantial legislative consensus rather than the preferences of a simple majority or a transient coalition. By imposing this high threshold, the Constitution protects itself against facile manipulation and underscores the solemn character of constitutional change.

Once an alteration is properly proposed and supported by the requisite number of legislators, the text of the proposed alteration is subjected to rigorous legislative deliberation. Both the Senate and the House of Representatives engage in debate, considering both the legal language of the proposal and its broader implications for governance, rights, and intergovernmental relations. In practice, this deliberative phase often entails referral to specialized committees, notably the Committee on Constitution Review, which is charged with detailed scrutiny of proposed alterations. Through committee hearings, expert opinions, and stakeholder inputs, the National Assembly tests the merit and necessity of change against constitutional principles and public interest.²⁰

The procedural steps that follow reflect the depth of deliberation required for constitution alteration. Constitutional proposals undergo multiple readings in both Houses and must be considered in identical form. Any divergence in text between the Senate and the House of Representatives necessitates reconciliation, typically through joint committees or further legislative engagement. Such mechanisms are essential in ensuring that the final product represents a unified legislative will, unencumbered by contradictory provisions that could undermine legal certainty.

The super-majority requirement extends beyond the initiation phase. For adoption, an amendment must still command the approval of two-thirds of the members present and voting in each House.²¹ This enduring demand for enlargement of support reinforces the principle that constitutional change should rest on broad political agreement. In effect, it subjects the proposal to what might be termed a double super-majoritarian filter: first, at the stage of initiation, and second, at the stage of passage. The dual requirement thus elevates constitution alteration above ordinary political negotiation and situates it within the realm of consensual law-making. Therefore, even absent members are counted in determining whether the threshold has been met.

While the National Assembly holds primary responsibility for initiating and passing constitution alterations, it cannot effect such alterations unilaterally. The Nigerian federal system envisages the participation of the Houses of Assembly of states as a necessary element in the process. After the National Assembly has passed a proposed alteration, the Constitution requires that it be submitted to the state legislatures for ratification.²² At least two-thirds of all the state Houses of Assembly must endorse the amendment before it can be promulgated.⁴ This requirement reflects the federal character of the Nigerian polity, acknowledging that constitutional changes often have implications for the distribution of powers and rights across the federation. The role of the National Assembly, therefore, is to lead the alteration process and also coordinate and collaborate with sub-national legislators to secure ratification. It is also worth noting that

²⁰ Aduba and Oguche, (n 1)

²¹ Section 9(2)

²² *Ibid*

the National Assembly's authority in constitutional alteration extends into the realm of facilitation and guidance. Given the complexity of constitutional texts and the procedural demands of ratification, the National Assembly often provides guidance and timelines to state assemblies to ensure that they understand the legal requirements and logistical steps necessary for proper ratification.²³ In this sense, in addition to acting as a legislative initiator, the National Assembly also acts as a custodian of the alteration process, overseeing its progress until all constitutional conditions are fulfilled.

Despite its central role, the National Assembly's power in constitution alteration is deliberately limited. It cannot act in isolation, nor can it manipulate the process to achieve partisan ends without broad consensus. The super-majority requirements and the demand for state ratification serve as structural checks against arbitrary or opportunistic constitutional changes.²⁴ Furthermore, while courts traditionally refrain from interfering in the substance of constitutional amendments, they may be called upon to adjudicate questions of procedural compliance. If there are allegations that due process was not followed, the judiciary serves as the final arbiter in determining whether the amendment process adhered to constitutional dictates.

In *AG Lagos State v. AG Federation & Ors*²⁵, the Supreme Court, while pronouncing on whether courts have the power to amend the Constitution, had this to say:

The Nigerian Constitution is called a Federal Constitution. But where there are unitary provisions contained therein, it is not the role of the Judge to expunge or jettison the provisions. That will be a clear interference with the role of the National Assembly under Section 9 of the Constitution. It is elementary law that a Judge has no jurisdiction to amend the Constitution by his pronouncements however learned they may be. The function clearly belongs to the National Assembly.²⁶

The implication of this judicial pronouncement is that the judiciary cannot rewrite the Constitution merely because certain provisions appear inconsistent with the federal character of the Nigerian state. Consequently, even where some constitutional provisions seem overly centralised or "unitary" in nature, judges are bound to interpret and apply them as they exist. They cannot strike them down simply because they disagree with their policy implications or believe they undermine federalism. Hence, this pronouncement reinforces the doctrine of separation of powers.

Constitution alteration is a legislative function reserved for the National Assembly and the State Houses of Assembly under section 9 of the Constitution, while the courts are limited to interpretation and enforcement. Thus, if Nigerians consider some provisions too centralised, such as those relating to policing, mineral resources, electricity, or local government administration, the proper remedy is constitution

²³ L Balogun, 'Constitution Review: National Assembly Promises To Transmit Report to State Assemblies' Voice of Nigeria, July 6 2025 <https://von.gov.ng/constitution-review-national-assembly-promises-to-transmit-report-to-state-assemblies/?utm_source=chatgpt.com> Accessed 20 July 2025

²⁴ S Egwu, 'The National Assembly and Constitutional Reform Agenda in the Fourth Republic' in L Hamalai and R Suberu (eds), *The National Assembly and Democratic Governance in Nigeria* (National Institute for Legislative Studies 2014) 215.

²⁵ (2003) LPELR-620(SC)

²⁶ Per Tobi JSC (as he then was), pp. 291-292 paras. G

alteration through the prescribed alteration process, not judicial activism. This case also highlights the supremacy of the Constitution. Courts derive their authority from the Constitution and must therefore operate within its limits. A judge who attempts to remove or alter a constitutional provision through judicial pronouncement would effectively be assuming the role of a constitutional lawmaker, which would amount to judicial overreach.

In practice, the National Assembly's role in constitution alteration has encountered both successes and challenges. The procedural rigour embedded in Section 9 has, on occasion, resulted in prolonged deliberations, reflecting the complexity of achieving widespread legislative consensus.²⁷ Nonetheless, this rigour also ensures that amendments are considered with the gravity they deserve, and that changes to the nation's fundamental law are deliberate, consensual, and reflective of federal interests. The National Assembly operates at the intersection of legal doctrine and political reality, safeguarding constitutional integrity while navigating the practical exigencies of democratic law-making. In essence, the role of the National Assembly in constitution alteration in Nigeria is marked by its centrality, procedural responsibility, and collaborative engagement with state legislatures. Through its super-majority requirements, bicameral deliberations, and coordination with sub-national legislatures, the National Assembly ensures that constitutional change goes beyond being the product of narrow political interest to a reflection of broad, federated democratic will.

3.2 The role of the Houses of Assembly of states

As the Nigerian Constitution embodies the principles of federalism, balancing the powers of the central government with the autonomy of the states. In this framework, the process of constitution alteration is deliberately designed to be rigorous, reflecting the significance and permanence of constitutional provisions. While the National Assembly initiates and deliberates on constitution alterations, the State Houses of Assembly play an indispensable role in ensuring that such alterations enjoy broad-based support across the federation. This dual-level participation reflects the federal character of Nigeria and acts as a safeguard against over-centralisation of legislative power.

Following the passage of a constitution alteration bill by both chambers of the National Assembly, the Senate and the House of Representatives, the bill must be transmitted to the 36 State Houses of Assembly for their consideration, as stipulated under Section 9(2) of the Constitution. This section requires that at least two-thirds of the State Houses of Assembly, equating to 24 out of 36, must approve the alteration before it can become law. The requirement of a supermajority ensures that constitutional changes are not dictated solely by the federal legislature, but rather reflect a consensus across the federating units. This mechanism is critical in maintaining the delicate balance between national authority and state sovereignty.

²⁷ A C Onuora-Oguno, 'A New Constitutional Moment? Nigeria's Legislature Revives Reform Ambitions in Sweeping Amendment Package' *Constitutionnet*, International IDEA, 4 June 2025 < https://constitutionnet.org/news/voices/new-constitutional-moment-nigerias-legislature-revives-reform-ambitions-sweeping-amendment?utm_source=chatgpt.com > Accessed 23 July 2025

The participatory role of the Houses of Assembly extends beyond mere approval. Although it is not expressly provided in the Constitution, the ethics of law-making demand that each House of Assembly is expected to scrutinize the contents of the proposed amendment, considering its implications for their respective states and constituents.²⁸ In practice, this deliberative function may involve committee reviews, public hearings, consultations with experts, and debates within the plenary. Through these processes, the Houses of Assembly ensure that the proposed constitutional changes are legally compliant, and socially and politically acceptable to the diverse interests represented at the state level. This inclusive approach enhances the legitimacy and durability of constitutional amendments.²⁹ A further dimension of the State Houses of Assembly's role is the temporal consideration of alterations. While Section 9 requires the approval of two-thirds of State Houses of Assembly, it does not prescribe specific timelines within which each House must deliberate and communicate its decision. In practice, this absence of statutory deadlines can result in prolonged consideration, with some Houses taking extended periods to reach a decision. Such delays may arise from political disagreements, procedural complexities, or competing priorities within state legislatures.

Although the Constitution does not prescribe a statutory deadline for State Houses of Assembly to act on amendment bills, prolonged delays have sometimes sparked public and political pressure and raise questions about procedural fairness. Courts generally have authority to review whether the required constitutional procedures have been followed, as seen in cases where the judiciary has examined aspects of the alteration process, such as the requirement for presidential assent in past litigation.³⁰ It is important to state that the Houses of Assembly act as deliberative forums where the interests of subnational governments are articulated and negotiated, thereby strengthening the consultative foundation of Nigerian federalism. The requirement for supermajority approval also functions as a check against potential domination by the National Assembly. By distributing the power to approve constitution alterations between the federal and state levels, the Constitution protects minority interests and prevents unilateral imposition of changes that may disproportionately affect certain states or regions. This mechanism embodies the principle of cooperative federalism, where meaningful participation of subnational actors is essential to the legitimacy of national legislation, particularly in areas as critical as constitution alteration.

Despite these advantages, the involvement of the Houses of Assembly introduces complexity and rigidity into the alteration process. While this rigidity safeguards the Constitution against arbitrary modifications, it may also slow down reforms that are urgent or widely accepted. Delays may arise from political disagreements within or among the State Houses of Assembly, procedural irregularities, or failure to comply with timelines. In such instances, judicial intervention may become necessary to ensure compliance with Section 9, reinforcing the rule of law in the amendment process.

The State Houses of Assembly occupy a pivotal role in Nigeria's constitution alteration framework. They act as guardians of state interests, deliberative bodies that vet

²⁸ S Oguche, 'Constitutional Quagmire in Kogi State: Examining the Failure of the Legislature and the Judiciary, [2017] 8(2) *Nigerian Journal of Legislative Affairs*, 81

²⁹ *Ibid*

³⁰ *Olisa Agbakoba v National Assembly & Anor (2010) 4 LLRN, 2078*

proposed changes, and essential participants in a process designed to reflect the federal nature of the country. Their engagement ensures that alterations are not imposed unilaterally by the National Assembly, but emerge from a broad-based, consensual process that strengthens national unity, respects state sovereignty, and preserves the legitimacy of the constitutional order. While the process may be cumbersome, it reflects a deliberate design to promote stability, inclusivity, and cooperative governance within the Nigerian federation.

3.3 The role of the Executive

The Executive occupies a significant, though comparatively limited, role in the process of constitutional alteration in Nigeria. Unlike the National Assembly and the State Houses of Assembly, whose approval is expressly required under section 9 of the Constitution, the role of the Executive is not directly elaborated in the constitutional amendment procedure. Nevertheless, the President may influence the process through the initiation of proposals, political advocacy, administrative coordination, and assent to alteration bills.³¹ One of the principal ways in which the Executive participates in constitutional alteration is through the initiation of Executive Bills. Although constitution alteration bills may be sponsored by members of the National Assembly as private member bills, the Executive may also originate proposals for constitutional reform where it considers certain provisions of the Constitution inadequate or outdated. These proposals are subsequently transmitted to the National Assembly in the form of bills for legislative consideration.³²

The Executive also plays an important agenda-setting role in constitutional reform. The President, as Head of State and Chief Executive of the Federation, may use public speeches, policy statements, executive communications, or consultations with political actors to mobilise support for particular alterations. In some instances, Presidents have established committees to review aspects of the Constitution and make recommendations for reform. These committees may conduct public hearings, consult stakeholders, and prepare draft proposals that later become the basis of amendment bills before the National Assembly.³³ Another major issue concerns presidential assent. Under the ordinary legislative process, once a bill has been passed by both chambers of the National Assembly, it is presented to the President for assent. The President may assent to the bill within thirty days or withhold assent, in which case the National Assembly may override the veto by a two-thirds majority of each House.³⁴ However, section 9 of the Constitution, which specifically governs constitutional alteration, does not expressly state whether presidential assent is required for a constitutional amendment bill to become law. This omission has generated considerable scholarly and judicial controversy.³⁵

The controversy became more pronounced during the 2010 constitutional amendment exercise when the National Assembly took the position that presidential

³¹ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999, ss 5, 9.

³² *Ibid*, s 58; Ben Nwabueze, *Presidentialism in Commonwealth Africa* (C Hurst & Co 1974) 189.

³³ O Oko, 'Constitutionalism and the Challenges of Constitutional Reform in Nigeria' [2009] 37 *Denver Journal of International Law and Policy* 213, 228.

³⁴ s 58(3)-(5).

³⁵ A B Mahmoud, 'Constitutional Amendment and the Question of Presidential Assent in Nigeria' [2012] 6(1) *Nigerian Judicial Review* 45, 51.

assent was unnecessary once the required legislative thresholds had been met. This position was challenged in *Olisa Agbakoba v National Assembly & Anor*³⁶, where the Federal High Court, Lagos Division, held that a constitution alteration bill could not become law without presidential assent. The court reasoned that because constitutional amendments are enacted through an Act of the National Assembly, they remain subject to section 58 of the Constitution, which requires presidential assent before a bill can become law. Justice Okechukwu Okeke held that the Constitution (First Alteration) Act 2010 remained “inchoate” until it was presented to the President for assent.³⁷ Although some scholars have criticised the decision on the ground that section 9 is self-contained and does not expressly require presidential assent³⁸, the prevailing constitutional practice in Nigeria has been to transmit constitution alteration bills to the President for assent after they have been approved by the National Assembly and the requisite number of State Houses of Assembly. Following the decision in *Olisa Agbakoba v National Assembly & Anor*³⁹, the National Assembly forwarded the amendment bills to President Goodluck Jonathan, who assented to them in March 2011.

The Executive’s involvement in constitution alteration also has considerable political significance. Since constitution alteration often affects issues such as federalism, revenue allocation, electoral reform, local government autonomy, judicial independence, and devolution of powers, executive support is frequently necessary for the success of major reforms. A President who actively supports a constitution alteration proposal may influence members of the ruling party in the National Assembly and encourage state governors to mobilise support within their respective Houses of Assembly.⁴⁰ Conversely, where the Executive opposes a proposal, it may become politically difficult to secure the required majorities at both the federal and state levels. At the state level, governors may also indirectly shape the position of State Houses of Assembly on constitutional amendment bills. Although governors have no formal constitutional role in approving alterations under section 9, their political influence over state legislatures may affect whether a proposed alteration secures the approval of the required two-thirds of the States.

However, the Nigerian position remains distinguishable from that of the United States. While the American Constitution clearly separates constitutional amendment from ordinary legislation and excludes the President from the process⁴¹, the Nigerian Constitution is less explicit. Article V of the US Constitution establishes a separate and self-contained procedure for constitutional amendment, distinct from the ordinary legislative process. It provides that amendments may be proposed by a two-thirds majority in both Houses of Congress or by a convention called at the request of two-thirds of the states, and must then be ratified by three-fourths of the states. As stated earlier, section 9 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 does not expressly

³⁶ (n 30)

³⁷ *Ibid*

³⁸ F Falana, ‘Constitutional Amendment: Presidential Assent Not Required’ *Sahara Reporters*, November 22 2010, < https://saharareporters.com/2010/11/22/constitutional-amendment-presidential-assent-not-required?utm_source=chatgpt.com > Accessed 15 August 2025

³⁹ (n 30)

⁴⁰ O N Ogbu, ‘A Critical Analysis of the Constitution First Alteration Act’ [2011-2012] 10 *Nigerian Juridical Review* 58, 63.

⁴¹ Article V of the Constitution of the United States.

require assent, but neither does it expressly exclude it. This ambiguity has created room for conflicting interpretations and judicial controversy. By contrast, the American position has been settled since 1798 and is generally accepted as part of the constitutional doctrine of separation of powers.⁴² Supporters of presidential assent argue that it reflects the principle of checks and balances in a presidential system of government. Since the President participates in the ordinary law-making process through assent or veto, they maintain that it is appropriate for the Executive to also participate in constitution alteration.⁴³ Opponents, however, maintain that allowing the President to veto constitution alteration may undermine the will of the supermajorities required under section 9 and permit the Executive to obstruct reforms with overwhelming democratic support.⁴⁴

From the above, the Executive does not possess direct constitutional authority to alter the Constitution independently, since this power is vested primarily in the National Assembly and the State Houses of Assembly. However, through the initiation of Executive Bills, policy advocacy, stakeholder consultations, political mobilisation, and presidential assent, the Executive remains an important actor in the constitutional alteration process. Its role is therefore both formal and informal, reflecting the broader political reality that successful constitutional reform often depends on cooperation among all arms and levels of government in Nigeria.

3.4 Nature of public engagement

Public engagement is an essential feature of the constitutional amendment process in Nigeria, ensuring that amendments reflect the collective will of the people and uphold democratic legitimacy. Section 9 of the Constitution requires that constitution alterations receive the approval of at least two-thirds of the State Houses of Assembly after being passed by the National Assembly. While this requirement focuses on legislative approval, the framers of the Constitution and subsequent legal literature have emphasised the importance of public participation in the process, as a means of strengthening transparency, accountability, and citizen ownership of constitutional reform.⁴⁵

Public engagement in constitution alteration typically occurs at multiple levels. At the federal level, the National Assembly may organise public hearings, stakeholder consultations, and committee meetings where citizens, civil society organisations, professional associations, and interest groups can provide input on proposed amendments. For example, during the 2010 and subsequent constitution alteration exercises, the National Assembly invited inputs from state governments, political parties, and civil society actors on proposals for electoral reform, devolution of powers, and judiciary restructuring.⁴⁶ Such consultations are intended to educate citizens, solicit their views, and ensure that proposed amendments address societal needs. At the state level, the State Houses of Assembly may also engage the public in their deliberations. Some State Assemblies organise town hall meetings, engage local traditional and religious

⁴² *Hollingsworth v Virginia* 3 US (3 Dall) 378 (1798).

⁴³ Falana (n 38); O Aguda, *Understanding the Nigerian Constitution of 1999* (MIJ Publishers, 2000) 142

⁴⁴ I B Lawal, "The Review of the Constitutional Amendment Procedure and Presidential Assent in Nigeria" (2015) 7(5) *Journal of Law and Conflict Resolution* 26-30.

⁴⁵ Mahmoud (n 35)

⁴⁶ *Ibid*

leaders, or circulate discussion papers to stakeholders.⁴⁷ These engagements serve as a feedback mechanism that allows citizens to participate indirectly in shaping the content of alterations before final legislative approval.

The Nigerian experience also reflects the influence of civil society and advocacy groups in facilitating public engagement. Organisations such as the Transition Monitoring Group (TMG), Yiaga Africa, the Policy and Legal Advocacy Centre (PLAC), and the Centre for Democracy and Development (CDD) have historically monitored constitution alterations processes, conducted civic education campaigns, and mobilised citizens to submit memoranda or petitions to legislative committees. These activities strengthen participatory democracy by allowing ordinary Nigerians to influence constitutional content beyond the narrow corridors of power. Despite these mechanisms, public engagement in constitution alteration in Nigeria faces notable challenges.

Firstly, participation is often formalistic and concentrated in urban centres, leaving rural populations underrepresented. Secondly, the technical complexity of constitutional language and amendment procedures may inhibit meaningful citizen input.⁴⁸ Thirdly, political considerations sometimes dominate the process, with ruling parties or influential governors shaping alterations behind closed doors, limiting the genuine impact of public participation.⁴⁹ Consequently, there is a growing intellectual call for more structured and widespread public engagement, including the use of digital platforms, civic education campaigns, and mandated public referenda for certain categories of constitution alterations.⁵⁰ While the Constitution provides the legislative framework for alteration, democratic legitimacy is reinforced when citizens are meaningfully involved. Improving the scope, depth, and inclusivity of public participation remains a pressing need to ensure that constitutional reforms reflect societal consensus and not merely political expediency.

4. CONSTITUTIONAL AMENDMENT IN GHANA

The constitution- amendment process in Ghana is governed by Chapter 25⁵¹ of the 1992 Constitution, which establishes a carefully structured and hierarchical framework for constitutional change. This framework reflects a deliberate attempt to balance constitutional rigidity with democratic adaptability, ensuring that while the Constitution remains stable, it is not immune to reform. At the heart of Ghana's amendment procedure is a dualistic structure that distinguishes between entrenched and non-entrenched provisions, each subject to distinct procedural requirements.⁵² The Constitution vests the power of constitution amendment in Parliament, providing that "subject to the provisions

⁴⁷ J A Aina, 'State Houses of Assembly and Constitutional Reform in Nigeria' [2023] 21(3) *Journal of Legislative Studies* 210, 218.

⁴⁸ A O Olukoya, 'Challenges of Public Participation in Legislative Processes in Nigeria' [2019] 13(1) *African Journal of Governance and Development* 45, 52.

⁴⁹ I E Nwafor, 'Political Influence in Nigerian Constitutional Amendments' [2020] 15(2) *Journal of African Political Studies* 77, 80.

⁵⁰ O C Udeh, *Strengthening Participatory Democracy in Nigeria: Lessons from Constitutional Amendment Practices* (CEDA, 2021) 34-36.

⁵¹ Constitution of the Republic of Ghana 1992, arts 289-292.

⁵² *Ibid*

of this Constitution, Parliament may, by an Act of Parliament, amend any provision of this Constitution.”⁵³

This formulation underscores the centrality of Parliament in the amendment process, situating constitutional change within the domain of representative democracy. However, this legislative authority is not absolute. Article 289(2) imposes procedural constraints, requiring that any amendment bill must be introduced solely for the purpose of altering the Constitution and must comply strictly with the procedures laid down in Chapter 25. Thus, Parliament does not operate as a sovereign constituent body, but as a constitutionally limited actor, bound by entrenched procedural safeguards. A defining feature of Ghana’s amendment regime is the distinction between entrenched and non-entrenched provisions. Entrenched provisions include fundamental aspects of the constitutional order such as the sovereignty of the people, the protection of fundamental human rights, the structure of government, and the amendment process itself.⁵⁴ These provisions are insulated from easy amendment in order to preserve the constitutional identity of the state.

4.1 Procedure for the amendment of entrenched provisions

The amendment of entrenched provisions under the 1992 Constitution of Ghana represents one of the most rigorous constitutional procedures in comparative constitutional law. This heightened rigidity reflects a deliberate intention to safeguard fundamental aspects of the constitutional order, such as human rights, the structure of government, and the sovereignty of the people, from impulsive or politically motivated alterations. The procedure is comprehensively set out in Article 290 of the Constitution and embodies a multi-stage process that combines legislative deliberation with direct popular participation.

The process begins with the initiation of an amendment bill and its consideration by the Council of State. The Speaker is under a constitutional duty to refer an amendment bill to the Council of State for its advice as a precondition for Parliament’s consideration of the bill.⁵⁵ The Council of State has 30 days, after receiving the bill, to render its advice. This implication is that the date of receipt of the bill is not reckoned with in the computation of the 30 days. Although it is not clear whether the advice of the Council is binding, it constitutes an important consultative step, ensuring that experienced statesmen and institutional actors provide input on the proposed amendment. This stage reinforces the deliberative nature of the process and introduces an additional layer of constitutional scrutiny.

The next phase is the publication of the proposed amendment. Article 290(3) requires that a bill seeking to amend an entrenched provision must be published in the Gazette. In addition to serving as a formal requirement, such publication serves a substantive purpose of notifying the public and stimulating national discourse on the proposed constitutional change. Following publication, the Constitution mandates a waiting period of at least six months before the bill can be introduced in Parliament.⁵⁶ This means that it is only six months post-publication that the Parliament can consider

⁵³ *ibid* art 289(1).

⁵⁴ *ibid* art 290(1).

⁵⁵ *ibid* art 290(2)

⁵⁶ *ibid* art 290(3)

the bill. Consequently, consideration by the Council of State and publication in the Gazette are two constitutional procedures and requirements that must be satisfied before Parliament can consider a bill for amendment of an entrenched provision. This further carries the implication that, from its initiation, a bill to amend an entrenched provision must spend a minimum of seven months before Parliament can consider it. This cooling-off period is designed to prevent hasty amendments and to allow sufficient time for public debate, civic education, and stakeholder engagement. After the expiration of the six-month period of publication in the Gazette, the bill is formally introduced in Parliament.

The first formal parliamentary step is first reading of an amendment bill. At the outset, the requirement that a bill for the amendment of an entrenched provision must first be read in Parliament signifies the formal initiation of the legislative process. After the first reading, the bill must be submitted to a referendum.⁵⁷ This indicates that, unlike ordinary legislation, the Constitution deliberately restricts Parliament from proceeding further with the bill after this initial stage of first reading. This limitation underscores the principle that amendment of the Constitution, especially in respect of entrenched provisions, transcends ordinary law-making and must not be left solely within the domain of representative institutions. This central feature of the provision of mandatory submission of the amendment bill to a nationwide referendum introduces an element of direct democracy into the amendment process.

Requirement of a referendum stands as the most distinctive feature of the amendment process for entrenched provisions. Article 290(4) provides that a bill submitted to a referendum must satisfy two stringent conditions. First, at least 40 per cent of the registered voters must participate in the referendum. Second, at least 75 per cent of the votes cast must be in favour of the amendment.⁵⁸ These dual thresholds serve as a powerful safeguard of constitutional stability. This turnout requirement is crucial in preventing constitutional amendments from being decided by a small or unrepresentative segment of the population. It ensures that the process commands a minimum level of national engagement and legitimacy. The turnout requirement ensures that amendments are not decided by a small or unrepresentative segment of the population. It ensures that the process commands a minimum level of national engagement and legitimacy.

Similarly, the supermajority requirement, which goes beyond a simple majority, demands an exceptionally high level of consensus among participating voters. This provision guarantees that only proposals with overwhelming national support can succeed. In effect, this stage transforms the amendment process from a purely legislative function into an exercise of direct democracy, vesting sovereignty in the electorate. The implication is that constitutional change must reflect not merely majority preference but near-unanimous agreement, thereby safeguarding the Constitution against frequent or partisan alterations. By requiring that the electorate at large participate in the decision-making process, the Constitution ensures that sovereignty is exercised through both elected representatives and directly by the people. This reflects the foundational democratic principle that the Constitution derives its authority from the will of the people and, therefore, can only be altered with their explicit consent. This dual mechanism serves as a protective barrier against impulsive, politically motivated, or narrowly supported amendments.

⁵⁷ *ibid* art 290)4)

⁵⁸ *ibid*

Where the referendum is successful, the bill proceeds to Parliament for formal enactment. Although the Constitution does not explicitly require a fresh supermajority vote at this stage, parliamentary approval remains necessary as part of the legislative process. Thereafter, the bill is presented to the President for assent, completing the amendment procedure.⁵⁹ The requirement of presidential assent integrates the Executive into the process, although its role is largely formal once the referendum and parliamentary stages have been satisfied. The President does not possess veto powers once the constitutional procedures have been complied with.

Article 290 of the Constitution of Ghana, 1992 shows that the procedure for amending entrenched provisions in Ghana is characterised by a combination of publication requirements, temporal safeguards, institutional consultation, and direct popular approval. This multi-layered process reflects a deliberate effort to protect the foundational elements of the Constitution while preserving the principle that ultimate constitutional authority resides with the people. Although the procedure is demanding and sometimes criticised for its rigidity, it remains a powerful mechanism for ensuring that constitutional change is both deliberate and democratically legitimate. The provision embodies a deliberate constitutional choice to make amendment of entrenched provisions both procedurally demanding and democratically grounded. By combining parliamentary initiation with direct popular approval subject to stringent thresholds, it ensures that constitutional reform is undertaken only where there is clear, widespread, and unequivocal support from the citizenry.

However, the rigidity of the entrenched amendment process has generated significant debate among researchers and policymakers. While the stringent requirements serve as a safeguard against arbitrary or politically motivated changes, they also create substantial practical obstacles to reform. Available experience in Ghana demonstrates that achieving the required 75 per cent approval in a referendum, coupled with the 40 per cent turnout threshold, is exceedingly difficult, particularly in a political environment characterised by voter apathy and logistical challenges.⁶⁰ As a result, many proposed amendments to entrenched provisions have either stalled or failed to materialise, leading some scholars to argue that the Constitution is overly rigid.⁶¹ Recent constitutional reform initiatives in Ghana further illustrate the enduring tension between stability and flexibility within rigid constitutional systems. The work of successive Constitution Review Commissions, particularly the 2010-2011 Constitution Review Commission, has consistently underscored the need to revisit entrenched provisions relating to the concentration of executive power and the limited autonomy of local government structures.⁶²

These reform efforts have been reinforced by subsequent policy and scholarly analyses, which highlight the persistence of an “imperial presidency” and the incomplete

⁵⁹ *ibid* art 290(6)

⁶⁰ C M Fombad, ‘Some Perspectives on Durability and Change under Modern African Constitutions’ [2013] 11(2) *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 382; A S Norman and K S Kantanka, ‘The Role of Referendum: A Case of Ghana’ [2020] 9 (6) *Global Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*, 1-5

⁶¹ D Ankar, ‘Rigidity Measures: On Constitutional Amendment’ [2017] 4(14) *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal* 84

⁶² Constitution Review Commission, *Report of the Constitution Review Commission* (2011); Government of Ghana, *White Paper on the Report of the Constitution Review Commission* (2012).

nature of decentralisation.⁶³ However, the entrenchment of these provisions, coupled with the stringent referendum requirements for their amendment, has significantly constrained the realisation of these reforms. Nevertheless, the procedural hurdles embedded in Article 290 continue to pose significant challenges to the implementation of such reforms. This has prompted calls for a re-examination of the amendment framework itself, including proposals to relax the rigidity of entrenched provisions through the introduction of alternative amendment mechanisms.⁶⁴ In particular, recent reform initiatives have advocated the creation of intermediate categories of constitutional provisions that may be amended by enhanced parliamentary majorities without recourse to a referendum, thereby mitigating the constraints imposed by stringent referendum thresholds.⁶⁵

4.2 Procedure for the amendment of non-entrenched provisions

The amendment of non-entrenched provisions under the Constitution of Ghana is governed by a comparatively less rigorous procedure than that applicable to entrenched provisions. This distinction reflects a deliberate constitutional design to the effect that while certain fundamental provisions are shielded by stringent safeguards, others may be altered through a more flexible, though still carefully regulated, legislative process. In the first place, a bill seeking to amend a non-entrenched provision must also undergo publication twice in the Gazette before it can be introduced in Parliament. Unlike publication for the amendment of entrenched provisions, publication of a bill for the amendment of a non-entrenched provision is made twice.⁶⁶ The first publication in the Gazette is required to last for at least 30 days before the second publication is made.⁶⁷ Before such a bill is introduced in Parliament, at least 10 days must have passed after the second publication in the Gazette. This publication requirement serves an important purpose of ensuring transparency and providing the public, civil society, and relevant stakeholders with adequate notice of the proposed constitutional change. It also creates an opportunity for informed debate and consultation before parliamentary action is taken.

Following this period of publication, the bill is introduced and subjected to the ordinary legislative stages in Parliament. As it is with entrenched provisions, the first legislative step is first reading of the bill after which the Speaker is required to refer it to the Council of State for advice, which shall be rendered within 30 days after receiving the Bill.⁶⁸ It is after the advice of the Council of State that the Parliament can proceed with second and third readings. Unlike ordinary legislation, the Constitution imposes a higher voting threshold for its passage. Another important feature of the process is the

⁶³ H K Prempeh, 'Africa's "Imperial Presidents": Assessing the Limits of Presidential Power in Ghana's Fourth Republic' [2008] 14(2) *UCLA Journal of International Law and Foreign Affairs* 1.; N Ayee, 'The Balance Sheet of Decentralisation in Ghana' [2008] 2 *Commonwealth Journal of Local Governance* 1.

⁶⁴ Constitution Review Committee, *Final Recommendations on Constitutional Reform* (2025)

⁶⁵ N Opoku, 'Ghana at a Crossroads: Another Attempt at Reforming its Constitution' Constitutionnet, 28th March 2025 < https://constitutionnet.org/news/voices/ghana-crossroads-another-attempt-reforming-its-defective-constitution?utm_source=chatgpt.com > Accessed 27 July 2025

⁶⁶ Art. 291(1)(a)

⁶⁷ *ibid*

⁶⁸ *ibid* art 291(2)

requirement that the bill must secure the support of not less than two-thirds of all the members of Parliament on both the second and third readings.⁶⁹

This supermajority requirement ensures that constitutional amendments, even in respect of non-entrenched provisions, are not passed by a narrow or transient majority, but rather reflect a broad consensus within the Parliament, thereby preserving a degree of constitutional stability. Once the bill successfully passes the third reading with the required two-thirds majority, it is then presented to the President for assent. Just like in the case of amendment of entrenched provisions, the President has no veto power over amendment bills passed by the Parliament. This is in view of the phrase “the President shall assent to it”⁷⁰ once a bill is passed as provided therein. Upon receiving presidential assent, the bill becomes law and the Constitution stands amended accordingly. In contrast to the procedure for entrenched provisions, there is no requirement for a referendum, which underscores the less rigid nature of the process.

4.3 Certification and presidential assent

As stated above, the President has no veto power over amendment bills duly passed in line with the provisions of the Constitution. However, article 293 establishes that a bill for the amendment of the Constitution, even after being duly passed in accordance with the prescribed procedures, does not automatically receive assent of the President. Unlike in ordinary legislation, the President’s role here is not discretionary in the usual sense; rather, it is conditional and procedural, guided by specific constitutional safeguards. First, the Constitution requires that any amendment bill presented for presidential assent must be accompanied by a certificate from the Speaker of Parliament. This certificate serves as formal confirmation that all constitutional procedures relating to the passage of the bill have been duly complied with.⁷¹ In the case of non-entrenched provisions, this would include requirements such as prior publication in the Gazette, observance of the necessary legislative stages, and the attainment of the prescribed two-thirds majority in Parliament. The Speaker, as the presiding officer of Parliament, acts as the authoritative certifier of legislative compliance. This requirement ensures procedural integrity and prevents the President from assenting to a bill that has not satisfied constitutional conditions.

Secondly, where the amendment concerns an entrenched provision, an additional and more stringent requirement is imposed. The bill must also be accompanied by a certificate from the Electoral Commission, signed by its Chairman and bearing the official seal of the Commission.⁷² This certificate confirms that the proposed amendment has been approved in a referendum conducted in accordance with the Constitution, specifically, that it met the turnout threshold of at least forty percent of registered voters and the approval threshold of at least seventy-five percent of votes cast. This requirement reflects the central role of direct democracy in the amendment of entrenched provisions and ensures that the will of the people, as expressed through a referendum, is formally authenticated before presidential assent is granted.

These requirements significantly constrain the President’s role in the amendment process. The President is not empowered to independently reassess the merits of the

⁶⁹ *ibid* art. 291(3)

⁷⁰ *ibid* art. 291(4)

⁷¹ *ibid* art. 292(a)

⁷² *ibid*, art. 292(b)

amendment or to veto it on policy grounds. Instead, the President's duty is largely formal and confirmatory. Consequently, once the requisite certificates are presented, indicating full compliance with constitutional procedures, assent must follow. In this sense, the provision reinforces the principle that constitutional amendment is ultimately governed by constitutional procedure and popular sovereignty, rather than executive discretion. Furthermore, the dual certification mechanism, by the Speaker and, where applicable, the Electoral Commission, serves as a system of institutional checks. It distributes responsibility across key constitutional actors and minimizes the risk of procedural irregularities. Parliament ensures legislative compliance, while the Electoral Commission guarantees the validity of the referendum process. The provision underscores a critical constitutional principle, that while presidential assent remains a formal requirement in the amendment process, it is strictly conditioned on prior procedural compliance. The President does not function as a veto-wielding political actor in this context but rather as a constitutional finalizer, acting upon verified compliance with the rigorous amendment procedures established by the Constitution.

The procedure under Ghana's Constitution, thus reflects a balance between flexibility and rigidity. On the one hand, the absence of a referendum makes it easier to amend non-entrenched provisions, enabling the Constitution to adapt to changing political, social, and economic circumstances. On the other hand, the requirements of prior publication, supermajority approval, and a mandatory interval between publications ensure that such amendments are not undertaken lightly or without adequate deliberation. The amendment procedure for non-entrenched provisions under the 1992 Constitution of Ghana is designed to facilitate constitutional evolution while maintaining institutional stability. It achieves this by combining legislative flexibility with procedural safeguards that ensure transparency, deliberation, and broad parliamentary consensus.

From the totality of the above, what is discernable is the fact that the constitutional amendment process in Ghana reflects a carefully calibrated balance between rigidity and flexibility, legislative authority and popular sovereignty. By distinguishing between entrenched and non-entrenched provisions and subjecting them to different amendment procedures, the Constitution seeks to protect its core values while permitting gradual evolution. However, the high thresholds and procedural demands associated with entrenched provisions raise important questions about the adaptability of the constitutional order in the face of changing political and social realities.

5. A COMPARISON OF THE PROCEDURES IN NIGERIA AND GHANA

A comparative examination of the constitution alteration procedures in Nigeria and Ghana reveals two distinct models of constitutional rigidity, each reflecting different historical experiences, institutional arrangements, and normative priorities. While both jurisdictions entrench their constitutions against facile alteration, Nigeria adopts a federal, legislature-driven approach, whereas Ghana employs a hybrid model combining parliamentary approval with direct popular participation through referendums. These differences have significant implications for the ease, legitimacy, and frequency of constitutional reform.

In Nigeria, the procedure for constitution alteration is governed by section 9 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999. The provision establishes a multi-tiered process requiring the approval of the National Assembly by a two-thirds majority

for general provisions, and a four-fifths majority for particularly special sections, followed by ratification by not less than two-thirds of the State Houses of Assembly. This framework reflects Nigeria's federal structure, ensuring that both national and subnational legislative bodies participate in constitutional change. Although the Constitution is silent or ambiguous on the necessity of presidential assent, the practice has generated considerable scholarly and judicial debate.⁷³ Nonetheless, the Nigerian model remains fundamentally legislative in character, with no requirement for direct popular ratification through a referendum. By contrast, Ghana's amendment procedure, as set out in articles 289 and 290 of the 1992 Constitution of Ghana, distinguishes between entrenched and non-entrenched provisions. Amendments to entrenched provisions require both parliamentary approval and a referendum in which at least 40 per cent of registered voters participate and at least 75 per cent of those voting approve the amendment.⁷⁴ This introduces a strong element of direct democracy, reflecting a deliberate effort to anchor constitutional change in popular sovereignty. However, the practical implications of these stringent requirements have been widely discussed in the literature.

Existing research suggests that Ghana's dual thresholds of turnout and approval are exceedingly difficult to satisfy in practice. Fombad observes that such demanding procedures are characteristic of rigid constitutions and are designed to insulate fundamental provisions from frequent alteration.⁷⁵ However, this rigidity has contributed to a pattern in which proposed amendments, particularly those affecting entrenched provisions, have either stalled or failed to materialise.⁷⁶ The aborted 2019 referendum on local government reforms illustrates the practical difficulty of achieving the required levels of participation and consensus.⁷⁷ As a result, scholars and policy analysts have increasingly characterised the Ghanaian Constitution as overly rigid, particularly in light of persistent challenges such as voter apathy, logistical constraints, and limited bipartisan cooperation.

The divergence between the two systems becomes even more apparent when one considers their respective reform trajectories. Nigeria, despite its complex and politically demanding procedure, has successfully undertaken several rounds of constitution alterations, including the First to Fifth Alteration Acts, which have addressed issues ranging from electoral reform to judicial administration.⁷⁸ These developments suggest that, while the Nigerian process requires substantial elite consensus, it remains operationally viable. In contrast, Ghana's experience has been marked by repeated but largely unsuccessful reform initiatives. The Constitution Review Commission established in 2010 identified key areas requiring amendment, including the concentration of

⁷³ A O Obilade, 'The President's Role in Constitutional Amendment in Nigeria' (2015) 9(1) *Nigerian Journal of Public Law* 45.

⁷⁴ Constitution of the Republic of Ghana 1992, arts 289-290.

⁷⁵ C M Fombad, 'Some Perspectives on Durability and Change under Modern African Constitutions' [2013] 11(2) *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 382, 398

⁷⁶ Institute for Security Studies, 'Amending Ghana's Constitution Can Protect Its Democratic Gains', 28th April 2022, *ISS Today* <<https://issafrica.org/iss-today/amending-ghanas-constitution-can-protect-its-democratic-gains>> accessed 4 August 2025.

⁷⁷ Opoku (n 65)

⁷⁸ Y O Oyewo and A O Ajayi, 'Constitutional Amendments and Democratic Governance in Nigeria' [2020] 12(2) *African Journal of Law and Criminology* 67.

executive power and the need to deepen decentralisation.⁷⁹ Subsequent policy documents and reform committees have reiterated these concerns, yet implementation has been constrained by the rigidity of entrenched provisions. This situation has prompted calls for a re-examination of Ghana's amendment framework itself. Recent reform proposals have advocated the introduction of intermediate categories of constitutional provisions or alternative mechanisms that would allow certain amendments to be effected without recourse to a referendum.⁸⁰ Such proposals reflect an emerging recognition that excessive rigidity may undermine the adaptability and responsiveness of the constitutional order. At the same time, defenders of the existing framework argue that the stringent requirements are necessary to preserve constitutional stability and prevent opportunistic alterations by political elites.

From a comparative perspective, the Nigerian and Ghanaian models illustrate a fundamental tension in constitutional design between democratic legitimacy and functional efficiency. Ghana's reliance on referendums enhances the democratic legitimacy of constitutional change by ensuring direct citizen participation, but it also raises the threshold for reform to levels that may be impractical in contexts of low voter turnout. Nigeria's model, on the other hand, privileges institutional negotiation and federal consensus, thereby facilitating incremental constitutional evolution while limiting direct popular involvement. Both Nigeria and Ghana embody rigid constitutional systems, but they operationalise rigidity in markedly different ways. Nigeria's legislative-federal approach, though complex, has proven relatively adaptable in practice, enabling periodic constitutional reform. Ghana's referendum-based model, while attractive for its emphasis on popular sovereignty, has encountered significant practical limitations, leading to reform stagnation in certain areas.

The participation of the Council of State in the legislative process in Ghana, particularly as a condition precedent to parliamentary consideration of certain constitutional bills, raises important questions regarding the doctrine of separation of powers. Under the 1992 Constitution, the Council of State is established primarily as an advisory body to the President, intended to provide counsel on matters of governance.⁸¹ Its institutional location is therefore within the executive framework, not the legislature. Against this background, its involvement in the law-making process appears, at first glance, to blur the boundaries between distinct organs of government.

The requirement that constitutional amendment bills be referred to the Council of State before Parliament proceeds may be viewed as a form of functional encroachment. It introduces an executive-linked body into what is traditionally a legislative domain, thereby creating the perception that Parliament's autonomy is procedurally conditioned by an external institution. Critics argue that this arrangement undermines legislative independence and allows indirect executive influence, particularly given that portions of the Council's membership are appointed by the President.⁸² This argument is strengthened by the fact that the Constitution does not provide the next step in case the

⁷⁹ Constitution Review Commission, *Report of the Constitution Review Commission* (2011).

⁸⁰ Constitution Review Committee, *Final Recommendations on Constitutional Reform* (2025).

⁸¹ Art. 89(1)

⁸² H K Prempeh, 'Africa's "Imperial Presidents": Assessing the Limits of Presidential Power in Ghana's Fourth Republic' [2008] 14(2) *UCLA Journal of International Law and Foreign Affairs* 1; C M Fombad, 'Some Perspectives on Durability and Change under Modern African Constitutions' [2013] 11(2) *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 382.

advice of the Council of State returns negative. Similarly, the Constitution is silent as to what happens where the Council of State does not render its advice within 30 days as provided. Consequently, it is doubtful whether the Council of State exercises a binding authority over Parliament or its role is purely advisory. It is also unclear whether Parliament retains full discretion to accept or disregard its recommendations.

The significance of referendum in the amendment of entrenched provisions in Ghana cannot be overemphasised. The provision vests sovereignty in the people and does not subject the popular will of the people to parliamentary or executive discretion. Hence, where an amendment proposal is approved in a referendum, neither the Parliament nor the President has power to decide to the contrary. Consequently, the Constitution provides that the Parliament “shall” pass the bill and the President “shall” assent. That accounts for the absence of any threshold for parliamentary passage after a successful referendum as such parliamentary passage is merely ceremonial. The comparative experience of the two countries thus underscores the need for a careful calibration of amendment procedures to balance the competing demands of stability, legitimacy, and adaptability in constitutional governance.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

From the above comparative assessment of constitution alteration practices in Nigeria and Ghana, there is a necessity for carefully tailored reforms that preserve constitutional stability while enhancing adaptability. The following recommendations proffered towards a more efficient constitution alteration process in Nigeria and Ghana:

i. Recommendations for Nigeria

(a) Clarification of the role of presidential assent

One of the most persistent controversies in Nigeria’s constitutional amendment process concerns the role of presidential assent. The absence of express constitutional clarity has generated conflicting interpretations and occasional executive-legislative tension. It is therefore imperative that this ambiguity be resolved either through authoritative judicial pronouncement or by explicit constitutional amendment. Such clarification would promote certainty, reinforce constitutional supremacy, and prevent undue executive interference in the amendment process.

(b) Introduction of structured public participation

Nigeria’s largely legislative alteration framework would benefit from greater incorporation of the public. Institutionalising structured mechanisms, such as mandatory public hearings, stakeholder consultations, and digital engagement platforms, would enhance the democratic legitimacy of constitutional changes without undermining the efficiency of the process. Nigeria could also draw lessons from Ghana to embrace referendum for alteration of special provisions, with liberal thresholds. This would align constitutional reform with contemporary expectations of participatory governance.

(c) Introducing timelines for state legislatures

While the requirement of approval by two-thirds of State Houses of Assembly reflects Nigeria’s federal character, it often results in delays and political bargaining. Introducing

clear timelines within which state legislatures must act, or adopting a default approval mechanism where no decision is taken within a specified period, would improve procedural efficiency while preserving the principle of federal participation.

(d) Institutionalisation of periodic constitutional review

To ensure that the Constitution remains responsive to evolving socio-political realities, Nigeria should institutionalise periodic constitutional review. Establishing a standing constitutional review body or mandating review cycles at defined intervals would facilitate continuous, structured reform rather than sporadic and reactive amendments.

ii. Recommendations for Ghana

(a) Relaxation of referendum thresholds

In Ghana, the stringent requirement of a 40 per cent voter turnout and 75 per cent approval for entrenched provisions has proven difficult to attain in practice. A reconsideration of these thresholds, either through their reduction or through the adoption of alternative quorum formulas, is necessary to make constitutional reform more attainable without compromising its legitimacy.

(b) Introduction of tiered amendment procedures

Ghana's constitutional framework would benefit from the introduction of intermediate or semi-entrenched provisions. Such provisions could be amended by a supermajority in Parliament without recourse to a referendum, thereby reducing the rigidity associated with entrenched provisions while maintaining appropriate safeguards against arbitrary change.

(c) Strengthening civic engagement and voter mobilisation

Given the centrality of referendums in Ghana's amendment process, efforts must be made to enhance citizen participation. This includes sustained voter education, improved electoral logistics, and the deployment of technology to facilitate broader engagement. It is essential to address voter apathy to ensure that referendum-based amendments are both viable and representative.

(d) Revisiting the Role of the Council of State

The involvement of the Council of State in constitutional processes should be carefully redefined to preserve the integrity of the separation of powers. While its advisory role may serve useful deliberative purposes, it should not operate in a manner that conditions or constrains parliamentary autonomy. Clarifying its role as strictly consultative would enhance institutional coherence. Consequently, there is a need to make further constitutional clarifications on steps to take where advice of the Council of State is negative or is not rendered within the stipulated period.

From the above, both Nigeria and Ghana must strive to strike an appropriate balance between rigidity and flexibility. Excessive rigidity risks rendering constitutional reform impracticable, while undue flexibility may expose the Constitution to instability. A calibrated approach is therefore essential to maintaining both durability and responsiveness. Transparency is critical to the legitimacy of constitutional reform. Both countries should ensure early publication of proposed amendments, facilitate stakeholder

input, and promote open legislative deliberations. This would foster public trust and accountability in the amendment process. Finally, both jurisdictions must invest in strengthening constitutional culture through public education and civic engagement. A well-informed citizenry is more likely to participate meaningfully in constitutional processes and to uphold constitutional values, thereby reinforcing democratic governance. While Nigeria requires reforms that enhance inclusiveness and procedural clarity, Ghana must address the practical constraints of its rigid amendment framework. In both cases, the overarching objective should be to design amendment processes that are legitimate, efficient, and capable of responding to contemporary governance challenges.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper has demonstrated that constitution alteration procedures in Nigeria and Ghana embody distinct yet convergent attempts to reconcile the competing imperatives of constitutional stability and adaptability. While both jurisdictions adopt rigid constitutional frameworks, they operationalise this rigidity through different institutional mechanisms, Nigeria through a federal, legislature-driven process, and Ghana through a hybrid model that incorporates direct popular participation via referendums. These design choices have produced divergent practical outcomes. Nigeria's system, though procedurally complex and politically negotiated, has enabled incremental constitutional reform, whereas Ghana's more stringent referendum requirements have, in several instances, constrained the realisation of proposed amendments.

The analysis further reveals that neither model is without limitations. Nigeria's alteration process is often criticised for its elite-driven character, limited public participation, and lingering ambiguities, particularly regarding the role of presidential assent. Conversely, Ghana's framework, while legally appealing for its emphasis on popular sovereignty, has proven excessively rigid in practice, with high thresholds that are difficult to satisfy in contexts marked by voter apathy and logistical constraints. The involvement of advisory bodies such as the Council of State also raises important questions about institutional boundaries and the balance of powers.

The comparative experience of both countries underscores a central lesson in constitutional design, which is that rigidity, though essential for safeguarding foundational norms, must not be so onerous as to stifle necessary reform. A constitution that cannot be meaningfully amended risks becoming disconnected from evolving political, social, and economic realities, while one that is too easily altered may undermine legal certainty and institutional stability. The challenge, therefore, lies in achieving a principled equilibrium between endurance and change. It is in this regard that the recommendations advanced in this paper assume significance. By clarifying procedural ambiguities, enhancing public participation, recalibrating amendment thresholds, and strengthening institutional coherence, both Nigeria and Ghana can move towards more balanced and functional constitutional amendment regimes. Such reforms would improve the mechanics of constitutional change and also deepen democratic governance and reinforce the legitimacy of the constitutional order.